

THE INFLUENCE OF ENTREPRENEURIAL MOTIVATION AND ENTREPRENEURIAL CHARACTERISTICS ON THE SUCCESS OF RONO DANGE MICRO-ENTERPRISE IN LERO VILLAGE, SINDUE DISTRICT, DONGGALA REGENCY

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the influence of entrepreneurial motivation and entrepreneurial characteristics on the success of rono dange micro-enterprises in Lero Village, Sindue District, Donggala Regency. The study used a quantitative method with an associative approach. The study population consisted of 30 rono dange entrepreneurs and the entire population was sampled through a saturated sampling technique. Data were collected through questionnaires and analyzed using multiple linear regression with the help of SPSS version 25. The results showed that entrepreneurial motivation had a positive and significant effect on business success with a calculated t value of 3.736 and a significance of 0.001. Entrepreneurial characteristics also had a positive and significant effect on business success with a calculated t value of 3.645 and a significance of 0.001. Simultaneously, entrepreneurial motivation and entrepreneurial characteristics had a positive and significant effect on business success with a calculated F value of 183.857 and a significance of 0.000. The coefficient of determination (R^2) value of 0.932 indicates that 93.2% of the variation in business success can be explained by these two independent variables, and the remaining 6.8% is influenced by other variables outside this research model. The results of this study prove that increasing entrepreneurial motivation and entrepreneurial characteristics can increase the success of the rono dange micro-business in Lero Village.

Keywords: Entrepreneurial Motivation, Entrepreneurial Characteristics, Business Success

INTRODUCTION

The micro-enterprise sector plays a crucial role as a key pillar of the national economy in Indonesia. Data from the Ministry of Cooperatives and SMEs shows that micro-enterprises not only contribute significantly to Gross Domestic Product (GDP) but also serve as the largest labor absorber, contributing to economic stability at the grassroots level (Kemenkop UKM, 2023). In addition, the adaptive nature of micro-businesses and their relative resistance to economic pressures make them a strategic instrument in efforts to reduce poverty and equalize welfare, especially in rural areas. Lero Village, located in Sindue District, Donggala Regency, is a coastal area with great potential for fisheries development, particularly anchovies. The village consists of five hamlets, with the majority of the population working as farmers (225), followed by fishermen (125), civil servants (67), laborers (31), private sector workers (21), and traders (10) (M. Amin & Laapo, 2021). However, according to data from the Central Statistics Agency (BPS), 243 people, or 11% of the total population of Lero Village, are categorized as poor or less prosperous, including those working as fishermen (Donggala Regency Statistics Center 2023). The development of rono dange culinary tourism on the Lero coast in recent years has encouraged the emergence of micro-enterprises based on processed anchovies, or rono (Santi et al., 2024, p. 1071). Rono dange, processed anchovies wrapped in sedge leaves and grilled over charcoal, is a popular and sought-after product, contributing to the income of the local community in Lero Village. However, field observations indicate that the success rate of these businesses is not evenly distributed, often not only determined by financial capital but also by internal factors such as entrepreneurial motivation and entrepreneurial characteristics to face business challenges. Several previous similar studies on fish processing MSMEs in other coastal areas have shown that the abundance of seafood does not automatically guarantee business success; success is strongly influenced by internal factors of the actors, particularly entrepreneurial motivation, entrepreneurial characteristics, experience, and business capabilities (Illahi Santoso & Reskiputri, 2025).

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On the other hand, studies on entrepreneurial motivation, competence, and characteristics in culinary and F&B MSMEs have shown a positive influence on business success. (Nurjanah et al., 2023). This finding is also in line with the research of Hasanah et al. (2025) which found that entrepreneurial motivation has a positive and significant effect on the success of MSME businesses. However, this previous study did not specifically examine MSMEs based on traditional processed micro-enterprises and small fisheries such as anchovies (rono) in villages such as Lero Village. Therefore, this study was conducted to analyze the influence of entrepreneurial motivation and entrepreneurial characteristics on the success of rono micro-enterprises in Lero Village, Sindue District, Donggala Regency to fill the gap in the literature in the field of MSMEs, especially those based on micro-enterprises in traditional culinary-based coastal fish processing. This research contributes academically by expanding the literature on local wisdom-based entrepreneurship. Furthermore, it offers practical implications as evaluation material for rono dange entrepreneurs to enhance their entrepreneurial motivation and product innovation. Managerially, the results of this study can serve as an empirical basis for the Lero Village Government and Donggala Regency Government in formulating empowerment policies. More effective and targeted MSMEs to strengthen the community economy and preserve the potential of local culinary areas.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Entrepreneurial Motivation

Entrepreneurial motivation is the internal and external drive within a person to start, manage, direct, and develop a business with the goal of achieving business success (Krishna 2020). Strong motivation can increase a person's desire to face challenges in the entrepreneurial world and achieve predetermined goals (Eliyana et al., 2020). Motivation derived from social support and recognition from the surrounding community also positively influences entrepreneurial spirit (Pinkovetskaia et al., 2020). This indicates that entrepreneurial motivation and social support are the main factors driving rono dange micro-entrepreneurs in Lero Village to develop local fisheries potential into productive culinary businesses. Efforts to achieve business success in this coastal area require a strong psychological commitment so that entrepreneurs can survive market competition and be responsible for creating innovative, sustainable anchovy processing. (Harmoko & Apriani, 2023)

A strong commitment to entrepreneurship in the seafood processing sector ultimately creates sustainable business resilience and creates jobs for the surrounding community (Clair et al., 2023). The success of micro-enterprises in the fisheries sector is inseparable from the ability of entrepreneurs to maintain their motivation amidst various operational challenges, such as fluctuating raw material prices, changing weather, and market demand dynamics (Syamsari et al., 2022). The development of entrepreneurial motivation can also be strengthened through entrepreneurship training programs designed to increase managerial capacity and product innovation for micro-entrepreneurs in coastal areas (Masrun et al., 2022).

Characteristics of Entrepreneurship

Entrepreneurial characteristics refer to specific traits generally possessed by individuals or groups involved in entrepreneurial activities. This forms the basis of behavior and attitudes that support efforts to develop and manage a business effectively (Ranti et al., 2024). Entrepreneurial characteristics are distinctive traits or forms of character or character, behavioral patterns, or special signs inherent in each entrepreneur in running and managing a business effectively to achieve the desired goals (Ramadhan et al., 2024). Based on Trait Theory (Trait Theory) explained by Stephen P. Robbins and Timothy A. Judge (2019), individual success in business is influenced by internal characteristics, such as self-efficacy, proactiveness, and achievement orientation. These characteristics are determining factors for the success of micro-entrepreneurs in Lero Village, where proactiveness and self-efficacy are needed to face the challenges of the traditional culinary business and optimize local potential competitively. This confirms that the unique character and behavior of entrepreneurs in the coastal area are internal instruments that drive business operations towards the desired success.

Business Success

Business success is a reflection of an entrepreneur's ability to manage resources to achieve predetermined business goals, both financially and non-financially. (Priyaa et al., 2025). Based on the Theory of Growth proposed by Edith Penrose (1959) and re-examined in a contemporary strategic management study by Jay Barney and Delwyn Clark in 2021, business success is influenced by managerial ability to manage and utilize internal resources effectively to achieve sustainable business growth. The success of the rono dange micro-business in Lero Village is greatly influenced by the entrepreneurial motivation and entrepreneurial characteristics of the business actors in

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managing the potential of anchovies into products with high economic value. Therefore, entrepreneurial motivation and characteristics play a role as the main factors that encourage the utilization of internal resources to achieve business success in the coastal area of Lero Village .

Conceptual Framework

Hypothesis:

H1: Entrepreneurial Motivation (X_1) has a positive and significant effect on Business Success (Y).

H2: Entrepreneurial Characteristics (X_2) have a positive and significant influence on Business Success (Y).

H3: Entrepreneurial Motivation (X_1) and Entrepreneurial Characteristics (X_2) simultaneously influence Business Success (Y).

METHOD

Types of research

This study uses a quantitative method with an associative approach to test the influence of entrepreneurial motivation. and characteristics of entrepreneurship towards business success micro rono dange in Lero Village, Sindue District, Donggala Regency. Associative research was used to analyze the relationship and influence between independent and dependent variables (Sugiyono 2023).

Population and Sample

The population in this study was 30 people, all of whom were rono dange entrepreneurs in Lero Village. Given the relatively small and limited population size, The sampling technique used was saturation sampling. According to Sugiyono (2019), saturation sampling is a sampling technique where all members of the population are used as research samples.

Data collection technique

In this study, data was collected through Primary data obtained by distributing questionnaires to 30 rono dange business actors in Lero Village, Sindue District, Donggala Regency. In addition to questionnaires, supporting data was also collected through field observations and documentation studies. Secondary data in this study came from scientific literature, such as books, journals, theses, and articles related to entrepreneurial motivation, entrepreneurial characteristics, and business success.

Data Analysis Methods

The data analysis technique in this study used SPSS, which includes instrument testing by conducting validity and reliability tests. The analysis stage begins with conducting classical assumption tests including normality tests, multicollinearity tests, and heteroscedasticity tests. After the model is declared to meet the requirements, the analysis continues to the statistical testing stage through multiple linear regression analysis and testing the coefficient of determination (R^2) to measure the level of the model's ability to explain variations in the dependent variable. Finally , the hypothesis is proven empirically through partial tests (t-test) and simultaneous tests (f-test).

RESULTS

Results of instrument validity and reliability tests

Validity and reliability tests were conducted to ensure that the research instrument accurately and consistently measures the variables, ensuring the data obtained is suitable for further analysis. Data processing and analysis were performed using SPSS version 2.5 software. The results of the validity and reliability tests are presented in the following table.

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Table 1. Validity and Reliability Test Results

Variables	Item	r count	r table	Validity statement	Cronbach's Alpha Value	Reliability Information
Entrepreneurial Motivation (X1)	X1	0.663	0.444	Valid	0,909	Reliable
	X2	0.879	0.444	Valid		
	X3	0.673	0.444	Valid		
	X4	0.765	0.444	Valid		
	X5	0.823	0.444	Valid		
	X6	0.801	0.444	Valid		
	X7	0.844	0.444	Valid		
	X8	0.801	0.444	Valid		
Entrepreneurial Characteristics (X2)	X1	804	0.444	Valid	0.942	Reliable
	X2	798	0.444	Valid		
	X3	807	0.444	Valid		
	X4	822	0.444	Valid		
	X5	754	0.444	Valid		
	X6	880	0.444	Valid		
	X7	853	0.444	Valid		
	X8	720	0.444	Valid		
	X9	804	0.444	Valid		
	X10	857	0.444	Valid		
Business Success (Y)	Y1	630	0.444	Valid	0.935	Reliable
	Y2	822	0.444	Valid		
	Y3	761	0.444	Valid		
	Y4	902	0.444	Valid		
	Y5	609	0.444	Valid		
	Y6	770	0.444	Valid		
	Y7	832	0.444	Valid		
	Y8	732	0.444	Valid		
	Y9	680	0.444	Valid		
	Y10	833	0.444	Valid		
	Y11	892	0.444	Valid		
	Y12	706	0.444	Valid		

Source: Processed data from SPSS 2.5 (2026)

Based on table 1 above, it can be seen from the results of data processing that has been tested on 20 respondents who have the same characteristics as the original respondents who will be studied, that of the 8 questions on the Entrepreneurial Motivation variable (X1), 10 questions on the Entrepreneurial Characteristics variable (X2), and 12 questions on the Business Success variable (Y) Overall, the items are declared valid. This is evidenced by the calculated correlation coefficient (r) value, which exceeds the r-table value of 0.444 (r-calculated > r-table). Furthermore, the results of data analysis show that the Cronbach's Alpha value for Entrepreneurial Motivation, Entrepreneurial Characteristics, and Business Success is greater than 0.60. Therefore , it can be stated that these valid items demonstrate reliability, so that the next stage of data processing can be continued.

Classical Assumption Test Results

Normality Test

According to Gunawan (2020) in Lesmana, (2021), data normality is a test used to determine and measure whether the data obtained has normal distribution or not, and whether The data comes from a normally distributed population. A regression model that is normally distributed or close to normal is considered a good regression model. The normality test used in

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This study is the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test.

Figure 1. Normality Test Results (PP Plot)

Source: Processed data from SPSS 2.5 (2026)

Based on the normality test results in the displayed PP Plot, the points are distributed around the diagonal line, and their distribution follows the direction of the diagonal line. This indicates that the regression model is suitable for use because it meets the normality assumption.

Multicollinearity Test

The multicollinearity test is a regression model test used to determine whether there is a correlation between variables. To detect the presence or absence of multicollinearity, the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) and Tolerance values are used.

Table 2. Multicollinearity Test

Variables	Statistical Collinearity	
	Tolerance	VIF
Entrepreneurial Motivation (X1)	0, 143	7,009
Entrepreneurial Characteristics (X2)	0.143	7,009

Source: Processed data from SPSS 2.5 (2026)

Based on Table 2, the results of the multicollinearity test show that the Entrepreneurial Motivation and Entrepreneurial Characteristics variables have a tolerance value greater than 0.10, namely 0.143, and a VIF value less than 10, namely 7.009. This indicates that there is no multicollinearity problem among the independent variables.

Heteroscedasticity Test

Heteroscedasticity is a condition where there is inequality of residual variance across all observations in a regression model (Subariyanto & Yulianto, 2021). The heteroscedasticity test is conducted to determine whether there is inequality of residual variance in the regression model.

Heteroscedasticity Test using Scatterplot

Figure 2. Results of Heteroscedasticity Test using Scatterplot

Source: Processed data from SPSS 2.5 (2026)

Based on Figure 2, the results of the heteroscedasticity test using a scatterplot indicate that the data points do not form a clear pattern. The data points are scattered and randomly distributed, both above and below the number 0 on the Y-axis. This indicates that the regression model used in this study is free from heteroscedasticity symptoms, thus the classical assumptions have been met.

Results of Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Multiple linear regression is a mathematical equation that represents the relationship between one dependent or response variable (Y) and two or more independent or predictor variables (X). The main objective of applying multiple linear regression analysis is to estimate the value of the dependent variable based on the known values of the predictor variables (Risnawati & Hamdani, 2025). Furthermore, this method is also used to determine the direction of the relationship between the dependent variable and each of the independent variables involved.

Table 3. Results of multiple linear regression analysis

	Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-6,750	3,307		-2,041	.051
	Entrepreneurial Motivation (X1)	0.787	0.211	0.498	3,736	.001
	Entrepreneurial Characteristics (X2)	0.754	0.207	0.486	3,645	.001

Source: Processed data from SPSS 2.5 (2026)

Based on table 3, the results of the multiple linear regression calculations produce the equation as follows :

Notes :

$$Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + e$$

Y = Business Success

a = Constant

X1 = Entrepreneurial Motivation

X2 = Entrepreneurial Characteristics

b₁ = Entrepreneurial Motivation

b₂ = Characteristics of Entrepreneurship

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$e = \text{Standard error of } Y = a + b_1 X_1 + b_2 X_2$

$Y = -6.750 + 0.787X_1 + 0.754X_2$ Based on the regression equation, the following explanation can be given:

- 1) The constant value of -6.750 indicates that if the Entrepreneurial Motivation (X1) and Entrepreneurial Characteristics (X2) variables are assumed to have a constant or zero value, then the value of the dependent variable (Y) is estimated at -6.750.
- 2) The Entrepreneurial Motivation variable (X1) has a regression coefficient (B) value of 0.787 with a positive direction. The partial test results show a t-count value = 3.736 with a significance level (Sig.) of 0.001. Since the Sig. value is <0.05, it can be concluded that Entrepreneurial Motivation (X1) has a positive and significant partial effect on the dependent variable. An increase in the motivation aspect will be followed by a significant increase in the dependent variable.
- 3) The Entrepreneurial Characteristics variable (X2) shows a regression coefficient (B) value of 0.754 with a positive direction. The t-statistic value obtained is 3.645 with a significance level (Sig.) of 0.001. Considering the Sig. value < 0.05, these results prove that Entrepreneurial Characteristics (X2) has a positive and significant partial effect on the dependent variable.

Overall, the results of this study indicate that entrepreneurial motivation and entrepreneurial characteristics have a positive relationship with business success . An increase in both variables will be followed by an increase in business success . In addition, entrepreneurial motivation is a variable that has a relatively greater influence than entrepreneurial characteristics in explaining variations in the success of the Rono Dange micro- business in Lero Village , Sindue District , Donggala Regency.

Hypothesis Test Results

Partial Test (t -Test)

The t-test is used to determine the partial effect of each independent variable on the dependent variable. The test is conducted at a 5% significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$) using a two-tailed test. The degrees of freedom value is calculated using the formula $df = n - k - 1$, where n is the number of samples and k is the number of independent variables. Based on research data with a sample of 30 respondents and 2 independent variables, the value of $df = 30 - 2 - 1 = 27$ was obtained. With a significance level of 0.025 in the two-way test and df of 27, the t table value was obtained of 2.052. The test criteria are if the calculated t value > t table and the significance value < 0.05 then the hypothesis is accepted .

Table 4. Partial Test Results

Coefficients ^a						
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients		t	Sig.	
		B	Std. Error			Beta
1	(Constant)	-6,750	3,307		-2,041	0.051
	Entrepreneurial Motivation (X1)	0.787	0.211	0.498	3,736	0.001
	Entrepreneurial Characteristics (X2)	0.754	0.207	0.486	3,645	0.001

Source: Processed data from SPSS 2.5 (2026)

Based on table 4, the partial test results show that the Entrepreneurial Motivation variable (X1) obtained a t-value of 3.736 with a significance value of 0.001. Because the t-value (3.736) > t-table (2.052) and the significance value of 0.001 < 0.05, then H1 is accepted. This means that Entrepreneurial Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Business Success. The Entrepreneurial Characteristics variable (X2) obtained a t-value of 3.645 with a significance value of 0.001. Since the t-value (3.645) > t-table (2.052) and the significance value of 0.001 < 0.05, H2 is accepted. This means that Entrepreneurial Characteristics have a positive and significant effect on Business Success.

Simultaneous Test (F-Test)

The F test is used to determine whether the independent variables simultaneously or have an effect on the dependent variable. In this study, the F test was conducted to test the simultaneous effect of Entrepreneurial Motivation (X1) and Entrepreneurial Characteristics (X2) on Business Success (Y). The F table value is determined based on the degrees of freedom of the numerator (df1) of k, namely the number of independent variables (2), and

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the degrees of freedom of the denominator (df2) of $n - k - 1$, namely $30 - 2 - 1 = 27$. At a significance level of 5% ($\alpha = 0.05$), the F table value is 3.35.

Table 5. Simultaneous Test Results

ANOVA ^a						
	Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	2021,439	2	1010.720	183,857	0.000 ^b
	Residual	148,427	27	5,497		
	Total	2169.867	29			

Source: Processed data from SPSS 2.5 (2026)

Based on the results of the F test, the calculated F value was 183.857 with a significance level of 0.000. The calculated F value (183.857) is greater than the F table (3.35) and the significance value (0.000) is less than 0.05. Thus, H_3 is accepted. This indicates that Entrepreneurial Motivation and Entrepreneurial Characteristics simultaneously have a positive and significant effect on Business Success.

Coefficient of Determination Test (R^2)

Coefficient of determination used to determine how much the independent variable is able to explain the variation in the dependent variable in the regression model.

Table 6. Results of the Determination Coefficient Test (R^2)

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Standard Error of the Estimate
1	0.965 ^a	0.932	0.927	2.34463

Source: Processed data from SPSS 2.5 (2026)

Based on the test results in table 6, the coefficient of determination (R Square) value was obtained at 0.932 (or 93.2%). This value indicates that the contribution or proportion of variation of the dependent variable, namely Business Success (Y), which can be explained simultaneously by the independent variables Entrepreneurial Motivation (X1) and Entrepreneurial Characteristics (X2) is 93.2%. The remainder (6.8%) is influenced by other variables outside this research model.

CONCLUSION

Based on the research results, it can be concluded that entrepreneurial motivation and entrepreneurial characteristics have a positive and significant influence on the success of the rono dange micro business in Lero Village, Sindue District, Malang Regency. Donggala. Partially, entrepreneurial motivation has a positive and significant effect on business success with a regression coefficient value of 0.787, a t-count value of 3.736, and a significance level of 0.001 (<0.05), so the first hypothesis is accepted. Entrepreneurial characteristics also have a positive and significant effect on business success with a regression coefficient value of 0.754, a t-count value of 3.645, and a significance level of 0.001 (<0.05), so the second hypothesis is accepted. Simultaneously, entrepreneurial motivation and entrepreneurial characteristics have a positive and significant effect on business success with an F-count value of 183.857 and a significance level of 0.000 (<0.05), so the third hypothesis is accepted. The results of the determination coefficient test (R^2) of 0.932 indicate that 93.2% of the variation in business success can be explained by entrepreneurial motivation and entrepreneurial characteristics, while the remaining 6.8% is influenced by other factors outside the research model. These findings indicate that increasing entrepreneurial motivation and entrepreneurial characteristics are important factors in increasing the success of the rono dange micro-business in Lero Village, Sindue District, Donggala Regency.

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